

COLLECTION OF SCIENTIFIC PAPERS WITH PROCEEDINGS OF THE

VII INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

**«Scientific practice: modern
and classical research methods»**

Boston
USA

February 14
2025

**LLC Boston Data Science Group &
NGO European Scientific Platform**

ISBN (online) 979-8-89217-802-0
ISBN (print) 978-617-8440-31-2

DOI 10.36074/logos-14.02.2025

LLC Boston Data Science Group | European Scientific Platform

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Boston,
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February 14,
2025

USA

«Primedia eLaunch»

Ukraine

«UKRLOGOS Group»

2025

UDC 082:001
S 30

*Chairman of the Organizing Committee: Goldenblat M.¹
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The organization on behalf of which the book is published:

¹ NGO European Scientific Platform, Ukraine

² LLC Boston Data Science Group, USA

Responsible for the layout: Bilous T. Responsible designer: Bondarenko I.

Recommended for publication by the Academic Council of the Institute of Scientific and Technical Integration and Cooperation. Protocol N° 6 from February 13th, 2025.

S 30 **Scientific practice: modern and classical research methods:** Collection of scientific papers «ΛΟΓΟΣ» with Proceedings of the VII International Scientific and Practical Conference, Boston, February 14, 2025. Boston-Vinnysia: Primedia eLaunch & UKRLOGOS Group LLC, 2025.

ISBN 978-617-8440-31-2

«UKRLOGOS Group» LLC, Ukraine

ISBN 979-8-89217-802-0 (PDF)

«Primedia eLaunch», USA

DOI 10.36074/logos-14.02.2025

Papers of participants of the VII International Scientific and Practical Conference «Scientific practice: modern and classical research methods», held in Boston, February 14, 2025, are presented in the collection of scientific papers.

The conference is certified by Euro Science Certification Group (**Certificate N° 22680 dated July 28, 2024**);

The conference is also included in the catalog of International Scientific Conferences by ResearchBib; and registered by State Scientific Institution «Ukrainian institute of scientific and technical expertise and information» in the database «Scientific and technical events of Ukraine» (**Certificate N° 414 dated June 12, 2024**).

Bibliographic descriptions of the conference proceedings are indexed by Google Scholar, CrossRef, OpenAIRE, OUCI, Scilit, Semantic Scholar, Mendeley, WorldCat and ORCID.

UDC 082:001

ISBN 978-617-8440-31-2
ISBN 979-8-89217-802-0 (PDF)

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ЯКІСТЬ ЗНАННЯ ПРОФЕСІЙНОЇ АНГЛІЙСЬКОЇ МОВИ ЯК УМОВА
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DOI 10.36074/logos-14.02.2025.080

NEUROPLASTICITY OF THE BRAIN AND MODERN PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES TO FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING: OVERCOMING AGE BARRIERS, STIMULATING COGNITIVE FUNCTIONS, AND IMPROVING PRONUNCIATION

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Relevance. Studying foreign languages is essential to modern life and part of cognitive development throughout ontogenesis, presenting unique challenges and barriers for people of various age groups. Neuroplasticity plays a significant role in learning and development processes. Neuroplasticity, also known as brain plasticity, is the process that includes adaptive structural and functional changes in the brain. A suitable definition is "the ability of the nervous system to alter its activity in response to internal or external stimuli by reorganizing its structure, functions, or connections" [17]. Research on neuroplasticity demonstrates that the brain can adapt and change neural connections throughout life; however, this ability decreases with age. Thus, the challenge arises of achieving the most influential foreign language learning at different ages by applying modern pedagogical approaches that consider the brain's neuroplasticity, its physiology,

and the characteristics of the individual language learner. This study is relevant for improving foreign language education and developing effective strategies to overcome psychological barriers.

Objective of the Study. To analyze modern views on the role of brain neuroplasticity in foreign language learning among different age groups and to outline pedagogical approaches aimed at overcoming age-related barriers, stimulating cognitive functions, and improving pronunciation.

Materials and Methods. The study materials include an analysis of current scientific literature on neuroplasticity, cognitive neuroscience, and pedagogy, specifically publications in *Frontiers in Psychology*, *Annual Review of Neuroscience*, *Neuropsychologia*, and others. Additionally, an anonymous interview was conducted to analyze the practical experience of teachers in German integration courses, individual English and German language tutors, and students. Methods of systematic literature review and analysis of scientific data on the impact of age on a person's ability to learn foreign languages, as well as information gathered during the interviews with the specialists mentioned above, were applied. The study also analyzes pedagogical techniques for improving pronunciation, mainly using articulation exercises with a pencil in the mouth to correct tongue positioning.

Results. The study found that the human language acquisition process is closely linked to various stages of brain development and its plasticity [1-11]. In children, neuroplasticity is at its peak, especially up to age 7, when language areas in the brain, particularly in the left hemisphere responsible for speech processing, are actively developing. Children build utterances subconsciously, absorbing speech patterns through listening and imitation. As noted by Kolb and Gibb [6], the brain creates numerous synaptic connections during this period, which makes children highly receptive to new language signals, allowing them to acquire languages rapidly. Children assimilate accents and pronunciation more quickly than adults since their brains don't engage in the same level of cognitive analysis and conscious control as adults do.

Brain plasticity is crucial in synapse formation phases, facilitating information transmission. Dendrites and spines show remarkable plasticity in response to experience, forming synapses within hours or even minutes after certain experiences. Although synaptic pruning is a significant feature of brain development, the brain continues forming synapses throughout life, essential for learning and memory. A fundamental difference exists between early synaptic formation processes and those in later development and adulthood. Early-stage synapses "await" experience to refine them; they are referred to as "experience-expectant" and are distributed diffusely throughout the brain. Later synapse formation is more targeted and localized in regions processing specific experiences, known as "experience-dependent" synapses.

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One exciting aspect of experience-dependent synaptic influence is that specific experiences not only lead to selective synapse formation but also selective synapse loss. Experience modifies neural networks by adding and pruning synapses, bringing us to brain plasticity [6]. Kolb and Gibb note that experience is not an isolated event; instead, as we go through life, it interacts, altering both behavior and the brain in a process often called metaplasticity. This, in turn, impacts brain development, such as synapse formation and changes in brain tissue according to external factors. Understanding these mechanisms helps refine better pedagogical strategies [6].

From a psychological perspective, children in early development stages lack full awareness of grammatical rules. They operate based on intuition and automatically create speech patterns based on heard information and context. This is because, at a young age, the brain is less inclined to deeply analyze speech information, as reflection and critical thinking—cognitive functions—are not fully developed [6]. However, this process is activated by the environment, allowing children to acquire languages naturally without conscious processing of information, unlike adults, who approach language learning more analytically.

It has been proven that understanding children's intellectual development stages at critical age periods is a crucial factor in teaching younger learners. Jean Piaget, a renowned Swiss psychologist, identified three main periods of intellectual development: the sensorimotor period (from birth to 1.5-2 years), the preoperational period (from 2 to 7 years), the concrete operational period (from 7 to 11 years), and the formal operational period (from 11 years and older). Each of these periods is characterized by specific cognitive changes that Piaget describes as positive for development but also containing limitations that need to be overcome in the next stage [10].

During the sensorimotor period (from birth to 1.5-2 years), a child begins to interact with the world through senses and movements, which develop their intellectual structures. A key achievement at this stage is the awareness of objects as existing independently, overcoming absolute egocentrism, which allows the child to separate themselves from the world of objects.

In the preoperational period (from 2 to 7 years), children cannot yet perform mental operations. Their thinking is guided by "seen" principles rather than logical ones. They progress through stages of semantic functions, egocentrism, decentration, animism, seriation, and conservation.

The concrete operational period (7 to 11 years) is characterized by developing symbolic thinking, speech, and imagination. Initially, the child's thinking is subjective and illogical. Exercises that help the child understand the constancy of volume, number, weight, and other object characteristics become essential at this

stage. Children form initial concrete operations by ages 5 to 7 and can perform more complex logical operations by 11.

The formal operational type (from age 11 onward) is characterized by the emergence of logical thinking and reasoning abilities. Other cognitive achievements at this stage include thinking about hypothetical possibilities and solving problems through logical conclusions and systematic approaches [10].

Biochemical aspects also play an essential role in the learning process. Neurotransmitters like dopamine and serotonin affect motivation for learning and the ability to remember new information. Elevated dopamine levels in the child's brain facilitate learning and support positive reinforcement in language acquisition. Studies by Hernandez [3] confirm that the child's brain is more capable of reinforcing new skills due to its plasticity and neuronal excitability, meaning that the neuronal and computational mechanisms underlying learning and sensorimotor integration assist in acquiring new skills.

Neuroplasticity slightly declines in adolescence (ages 14-18), yet the brain remains flexible. However, new barriers, mainly psychological, begin to emerge, as emotional imbalance often increases in teenagers, potentially causing motivation issues that directly affect their language learning ability. This is due to the prefrontal cortex not being fully developed and responsible for planning, self-organization, and emotional control. As Antoniou et al. [12] noted, creating pedagogical methods that involve cognitive stimulation and emotional support is essential for teaching this age group, as it maintains interest and engagement in the learning process. Additionally, instructors should recognize that the brain develops heterogeneously, which should be considered in teaching.

According to Antoniou and co-authors [12], foreign language learning can even be a cognitive therapy method for teenagers, as it stimulates cognitive functions and enhances self-control. The support teachers provide to students in this age group includes emotional support and motivation, which may help overcome age-related barriers.

Biochemically, teenagers often face hormonal changes affecting their concentration and memory. For instance, elevated cortisol levels during stress can interfere with information retention, creating additional barriers to language learning. Psychological support and motivational approaches can potentially reduce these barriers and improve learning effectiveness.

In young adults (ages 19-28), further reduction in neuroplasticity is observed, but due to well-developed cognitive functions (reflection, analytical thinking, planning), they can successfully adapt new knowledge, especially in language. Adult learning becomes more conscious, requiring active participation. Motivation and regular practice, which stimulate synaptic plasticity in the brain, become essential [5].

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Another important factor, often decisive in the genesis of a psychological barrier, should be noted. It stems not only from uncertainty about one's foreign language vocabulary but is also driven by the fear of making mistakes during conversation. To overcome this fear, it is advised that teachers refrain from immediately correcting students by interrupting their responses. Instead, the teacher may note or remember the errors and discuss them afterward. This allows for a review of grammatical patterns and promotes a better rapport with the student. Learners are encouraged to actively use learned patterns in conversation and integrate them into their daily lives. One interviewee in this study remarked that "what helped him was attempting to speak with unfamiliar people". According to him, the more questions, the better; one can only overcome fear by confronting it. After emigrating, he started working, which helped him greatly as he constantly engaged in conversation.

In addressing organizational matters and providing explanations during foreign language lessons, it is recommended to use only the language being studied. Thus, the experience of integration courses in Germany demonstrates that learning German through German is an effective strategy for acquiring a new language [15].

For older adults (29–42 years), foreign language acquisition is challenged by decreased neuroplasticity and cognitive abilities, particularly working memory. As Boyke states [8], while the brain remains capable of learning, it requires more active stimulation methods (pronunciation exercises and speech correction techniques). For instance, exercises with a pencil or pen to adjust tongue position help develop proper articulation during English and German language learning. The practical experiences of surveyed teachers and students in this study indicate that incorporating this technique positively impacts pronunciation and reduces accent intensity. Biochemical processes, such as the reduction in dopamine levels and other neurotransmitters, may also affect motivation for learning in this age group [16].

Incorporating knowledge of neuroplasticity and the specifics of biochemical processes over a person's lifespan can help create more effective learning methods for different age groups.

This study involved 30 students learning German and English. All students were divided into three age groups: 1 - 11 participants aged 14–17, 2 - 13 participants aged 18–34, and 3 - 6 participants aged 35–42.

Pronunciation improvement exercises were performed over three months, and results were observed in all age groups. However, the time required to achieve significant changes varied depending on the participant group. In the first group (aged 14–17), 82% noticed pronunciation improvements within three weeks,

suggesting that younger learners can achieve visible results quickly. In the second group (ages 18–34), 77% demonstrated significant pronunciation improvement in a month and a half. In the third group (ages 35–42), 67% of participants exhibited positive changes in pronunciation noticeable after two months.

Notably, participants in the second and third groups could acquire some grammatical constructions through passive learning via singing, which also positively impacted their vocabulary. In contrast, the first group showed minimal vocabulary growth through singing with a pencil in the mouth. This indicates that the effectiveness of this technique varies across age groups.

Thus, the study results demonstrate that using a pencil or pen in the mouth is an effective method for improving pronunciation in all age groups. However, combining this approach with other vocabulary development and grammar acquisition methods is important, especially among adult participants.

These results confirm the effectiveness of articulation exercises, such as holding an object (like a pen) in the mouth. Studies show that such practice enhances tongue movement control, aiding the formation of correct speech sounds and articulation [13-14]. Furthermore, the exercises stimulate brain neuroplasticity, contributing to the overall development of speech skills, particularly in children and young people, but may also benefit adult learners [14]. Therefore, the study results emphasize the value of integrating innovative teaching methods into the foreign language learning process to achieve greater effectiveness.

In the age group of 29–42 years, foreign language learning is complicated by decreased cognitive abilities, mainly working memory, and reduced neuroplasticity. As research by Boyke et al. shows [8], the adult brain remains adaptable despite these limitations through constant learning and repetition. Regular training, structured learning methods, and exercises to maintain cognitive activity, such as listening to and repeating complex phrases, can help maintain high learning efficiency.

Conclusions. This study confirmed the key role of brain neuroplasticity and cognitive processes in language learning at different stages of life. During childhood, high neuroplasticity and active biochemical support allow children to acquire speech patterns easily without conscious analysis. The adolescent period is marked by a gradual decline in neuroplasticity, but the brain remains flexible enough for effective learning with emotional support and appropriate pedagogical methods. In young adults (19–28 years), decreased neuroplasticity is compensated for by mature cognitive functions, and for older adults (29–42 years), effective learning requires more structured approaches and exercises to maintain brain activity.

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Articulation exercises, such as the pencil method for improving pronunciation, promote the formation of correct speech skills and clear articulation, increasing the success of foreign language acquisition in older age groups.

Thus, successful foreign language acquisition requires consideration of neurobiological changes in the brain throughout life. Understanding neuroplasticity and biochemical processes provides a foundation for developing effective teaching methods for all age categories. The results suggest adapting pedagogical approaches to age-related brain development and cognitive processes to maximize the effectiveness of foreign language learning.

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УДК 082:001
S 30

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Заступник голови оргкомітету: Bailey С.²

Організації, від імені яких публікується видання:

¹ ГО «Європейська наукова платформа», Україна

² LLC Boston Data Science Group, США

Верстка: Білоус Т.В.

Дизайн: Бондаренко І.В.

Рекомендовано до видання Вченою Радою Інституту науково-технічної інтеграції та співпраці. Протокол № 6 від 13.02.2025 року.

S 30 **Scientific practice: modern and classical research methods:** збірник наукових праць «ΛΟΓΟΣ» з матеріалами VII Міжнародної науково-практичної конференції, м. Бостон, 14 лютого 2025 р. – Вінниця-Бостон: ТОВ «УКРЛОГОС Груп», Primedia eLaunch, 2025. 406 с.

ISBN 978-617-8440-31-2

ТОВ «УКРЛОГОС Груп», Україна

ISBN 979-8-89217-802-0 (PDF)

«Primedia eLaunch», США

DOI 10.36074/logos-14.02.2025

В збірнику викладено статті та тези учасників VII Міжнародної науково-практичної конференції «Scientific practice: modern and classical research methods», що відбулась 14 лютого 2025 року в м. Бостон, США.

Конференція сертифікована Euro Science Certification Group
(Сертифікат № 22680 від 28 липня 2024 р.);

Конференцію, також, включено до Каталогу міжнародних наукових конференцій ResearchBib та зареєстровано Державною науковою установою «Український інститут науково-технічної експертизи та інформації» в базі даних «Науково-технічні заходи України» (Посвідчення № 414 від 12 червня 2024 р.).

Всі роботи збірника відображені та/або індексуються в Google Scholar, CrossRef, OpenAIRE, OUCI, Scilit, Semantic Scholar, Mendeley, WorldCat and ORCID.

УДК 082:001

ISBN 978-617-8440-31-2
ISBN 979-8-89217-802-0 (PDF)

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НАУКОВЕ ВИДАННЯ

ЗБІРНИК НАУКОВИХ ПРАЦЬ

З МАТЕРІАЛАМИ VII МІЖНАРОДНОЇ
НАУКОВО-ПРАКТИЧНОЇ КОНФЕРЕНЦІЇ

**«SCIENTIFIC PRACTICE: MODERN AND
CLASSICAL RESEARCH METHODS»**

14 лютого 2025 у м. Бостон, США

Англійською та українською мовами

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Опубліковано (PDF): 21.02.2025. Підписано до друку: 14.02.2025.
Папір офсетний. Гарнітура Arial. Цифровий друк. Формат 70×100/16.
Умовно-друк. арк. 32,99. Замовлення № 25/002.
Тираж: 100 екземплярів. Віддруковано з готового оригінал-макету.

Видавець та організаційний комітет конференції:

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URL: www.archive.logos-science.com

Співорганізатор конференції:

LLC Boston Data Science Group
MA 02421; USA. Lexington, 36 Fairbanks RD

Видавець [PDF]: Primedia E-launch LLC
KS 5518, United States, Kansas, Shawnee, Flint St. E-mail: info@primediaelaunch.com.

Виготовлювач [друковані копії]: ТОВ «УКРЛОГОС Груп».
21005, Україна, м. Вінниця, вул. Зодчих, 18, офіс 81. E-mail: info@ukrlogos.in.ua
Свідоцтво суб'єкта видавничої справи: ДК № 7860 від 22.06.2023.

SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION

COLLECTION OF SCIENTIFIC PAPERS

WITH PROCEEDINGS OF THE VII INTERNATIONAL
SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

**«SCIENTIFIC PRACTICE: MODERN AND
CLASSICAL RESEARCH METHODS»**

February 14, 2025 in Boston, USA

English and Ukrainian

*All papers have been reviewed
Organizing committee may not agree with the authors' point of view
Authors are responsible for the correctness of the papers' text*

Published (PDF): 21.02.2025. Signed for printing: 14.02.2025.
Format 70×100/16. Offset Paper. The headset is Arial. Digital printing.
Conventionally printed sheets 32,99.
Circulation: 100 copies. Printed from the finished original layout.

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LLC Boston Data Science Group
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Publisher [PDF]: Primedia E-launch LLC
KS 5518, United States, Kansas, Shawnee, Flint St.. E-mail: info@primediaelaunch.com.

Publisher [printed copies]: LLC UKRLOGOS Group
21005, Ukraine, Vinnytsia, Zodchykh str. 18, office 81. E-mail: info@ukrlogos.in.ua
Certificate of the subject of the publishing business: ДК № 7860 of 22.06.2023.